

1 **Phosphatase vulnerabilities in humans whose genomes contain mutations in BRCA1.**

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6 We measured whole transcription in human mammary gland organoids and in cells with engineered
7 deletion of *BRCA1*. We also studied the transcriptome of non-transformed (pre-cancerous) mammary
8 epithelial tissues from humans with BRCA1 mutation and of control, non-BRCA1 mutated humans to
9 understand how Brca1 controlled the transcriptome. We report here discovery of phosphatase
10 dependencies specific to the BRCA1-deficient genotype in human breast cancer. These enzymes included
11 *PPP4C* and *PPP1R3C*. A function for these enzymes in regulation of the actin cytoskeleton was
12 suggested by co-regulation of cofilin (CFL1) and profilin (PFN1) by PPP4C and PPP1R3C. A metabolic
13 function for the enzymes in the cell separate from a function in the cytoskeleton was indicated by intimate
14 co-regulation with branched chain ketoacid dehydrogenase kinase (BCKDK), aldolase A
15 (fructose-bisphosphate; ALDOA), and muscle pyruvate kinase (PKM).
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